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Research Article

Optimization Of Dolutegravir Solid Dispersion To Enhance Its Solubility By 2² Factorial Designs

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the present study is to enhance, optimise the solubility and to formulate Dolutegravir tablets by using Design Expert® 12 software. Dolutegravir is a HIV-1 integrase inhibitor that blocks the strand transfer step of the integration of the viral genome into the host cell. Dolutegravir belongs to BCS class II. Solubility of Dolutegravir -0.095mg/ml in water. Phase solubility and saturation solubility studies of the drug were performed in various solvents. Drug solubility was enhanced using various polymers and different methods. The study was carried out to design an optimised formulation of Dolutegravir solid dispersion using a blend of two solubility enhancers. Interaction effect of Kollidon and Polaxmer-237 1:1 ratio enhances the solubility of the drug. The optimised solid dispersion mixture was used to formulate solid dosage forms (tablets). 89% drug release was observed in 1.5hrs from tablets. Electron micrograph for solid dispersion of Dolutegravir was obtained using scanning electron microscope. Drug Excipient Compatibility Studies of Drug and excipients were performed using TLC and FTIR.

INTRODUCTION

The majority of drugs on the market are designed for administration via the oral route; this is the most convenient method of drug delivery. The solubility of drug compounds in water is such an important issue in drug development. If a drug has poor oral bioavailability, methods to Improve its solubility are often considered first in an attempt to move compounds from BCS [2,4] Various

methods were employed to enhance the solubility of class II drugs.[1,6,7.] Solid dispersion is one that is widely used to describe a system in which drug particles are homogeneously dispersed in a carrier matrix [1] Factorial designs (FD, full or fractional), also known as experimental designs for the first-degree models, are the most popular response surface designs. In the present study we

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tried to enhance the solubility of Dolutegravir class-II using various polymers and different methods. The maximum solubility was enhanced using polymers Kollidon and Polaxmer-237. These two polymers were used to optimize the solid dispersion formulation by 22 factorial design using Design Expert® 12 software. The optimised solid dispersion mixture was used to formulate tablets. We determined the Drug excipient incompatibility studies using TLC and FTIR. SEM photographs of Dolutegravir exhibited high crystallinity with several planes of surfaces. Polaxamer 237 exhibited a spherical shape of granular form of beads. Blend shows that the drug was adsorbed on to the spherical beads and there by enhanced the solubility of dolutegravir and reduces the crystallinity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Preformulation studies:

Phase Solubility: Phase solubility analysis is the quantitative determination of the purity of a substance through the application of precise solubility measurements. A 50 mg of dolutegravir drug was taken and it is solubilised in 50ml of phosphate buffer 6.8pH and the results were discussed in later section. **Saturation Solubility Studies** Dolutegravir solubility was determined by shake-flask method. Plain dolutegravir in excess quantity was placed in separate glass stoppered flasks containing few ml of distilled water. The samples were placed on magnetic stirrer at 37°C and 100 rpm until equilibrium was achieved (24 h). The aliquots were filtered through wattman No.41 filter paper. The filtrates were diluted appropriately in distilled water and assayed spectrophotometrically at 254 nm. The results were given in later section.

Drug Excipient Compatibility Studies [3]

Study of drug-excipient compatibility is an important phase in the pre-formulation stage of drug development. The potential interactions between drugs and excipients have effects on the

chemical, physical, bioavailability and stability of the dosage form. Drug-excipient compatibility studies to provide data for drug-excipient interaction which can further help in selection of excipient for the development of stable dosage form. It Includes TLC and FTIR studies

Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC):

A simple TLC technique is used in order to know the interaction between drug and excipients as a part of Preformulation studies. For this the pure drug, polymer and its combinations with the polymers were subjected to chromatographic studies.

TLC system

Precoated TLC plates:

Mfg. by S.d fine chemicals silica gel G

Adsorbent Layer:

Mfg. by S.d fine chemicals silica gel G

Layer Thickness:

200µm, Separation Technique: Ascending, Size: 10 × 20cm

Mobile phase:

chloroform: Benzene: Methanol: Acetic acid 6: 3: 1: 0.1 Three spots were made on the TLC sheet

.Drug:

Dolutegravir, B. Excipient: Polaxmer -237, C. Drug + Excipient

Amount applied:

10µL, Detection: UV chamber. The results were given in later section.

Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR):

It is used to identify the compatibility between drug and excipient. A common FTIR spectrometer consists of a source, interferometer, sample compartment, detector, amplifier, A/D convertor, and a computer. The results were given in later section

Preparation Of Solid Dispersion:

Solid dispersion of dolutegravir with β-cyclodextrin, kollidon, Soluplus polaxamers 188, 237 and 408 were prepared in the ratios of 1:1, 1:2,

1:3 of drug-carrier. Physical mixture techniques have been used for the preparation of solid dispersion in the present study. In this method, 10mg, dolutegravir was accurately weighed and mixed thoroughly; physical mixtures were formulated by mixing drug and carrier in geometric proportions using a spatula without applying pressure. The solid dispersions were passed th

rough a No. 60 sieve and stored over anhydrous calcium chloride in a desiccator. Six polymers were used to test the solubility (Total 18 formulations). Out of six polymers two were found to be better. By considering those two polymers few more methods like solvent evaporation method and micro-oven method were employed. F8 and F14 formulations are subjected to solvent evaporation and micro oven method).

Table No:1 Formulation Of Solid Dispersions Using Physical Mixture Method

SNO	Polymers(mg)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
1	Soluplus	20	40	60	-	-	-	-	-
2	β - cyclodextrin	-	-	-	20	40	60	-	-
3	Kollidon	-	-	-	-	-	-	20	40
4	Drug	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20

Table No:2 Formulation Of Solid Dispersions Using Physical Mixture Method

SNO	Polymers(mg)	F10	F11	F12	F13	F14	F15	F16	F17
1	P-188	20	40	60	-	-	-	-	-
2	P-237	-	-	-	20	40	60	-	-
3	P-407	-	-	-	-	-	-	20	40
4	Drug	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20

Table No: 3 Formulation Of Solid Dispersion Using Solvent Evaporation Method And Micro-Oven Method

Polymers(mg)	Solvent evaporation method	Micro-oven method
Polaxamer 237	F19	F21
Kollidon	F20	F22

F19 formulation formulated using drug and polaxmer-237 (1:2) has shown better solubility of the drug among all. This formulation was selected for dosage form development. Combinations of Kollidon and Polaxmer- 237 were used for optimization studies using DOE version12. In-vitro dissolution testing methodologies can be used to determine the key factors that influence the performance of a drug. 900ml of required buffer was placed into dissolution beaker and switch on the dissolution apparatus. The following conditions are maintained Bath and bowl temperature- 37°C. Buffer – 900ml, Stirrer rotation speed – 50rpm When these conditions are reached the tablet was placed in the dissolution medium. Sampling was done properly. i.e., 5ml of sample is withdrawn from the medium with specified time

interval (15/30min) for testing and 5ml buffer is replaced to the medium. The withdrawn sample is tested for absorbance in UV spectrophotometer and results were discussed in later section.

Apparatus: Lab India DS8000,

Rpm: 50 rpm,

Medium: 6.8 pH phosphate buffer

Volume: 900 ml,

Temperature: 37°C \pm .5°C

Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) analysis [5]

Electron micrographs for solid dispersion of Dolutegravir and polaxamer 237 in 1:2 ratio was obtained using scanning electron microscope (SEM; Joel JSM-5910, Japan) operating at 10 kV.. To study themorphology of solid dispersion of Dolutegravir and polaxamer 237 micrographs with

different magnification were obtained and results were discussed in later section.

Factorial Design [11]

Optimization helps in determining the dependent and independent factors and how they exert their effect on the characteristics of the formulation. Four formulations were optimised using design expert software 12.0. Optimized formulation was selected based on Statistical analysis. The study

was carried out to design an optimised formulation of dolutegravir solid dispersion using a blend of two solubility enhancers- Kollidon and polaxamer 237. Two independent variables (kollidon and polaxamer 237) and two levels were set as high and low. The study was designed to be a 2² fractional design, meaning that two variables were studied at two different levels

Table No: 4. Standard symbols for particular ratio of polymers for 2² design with two factors and two levels

Standard	Run	F1	F2
1	1	-1	-1
2	2	+1	-1
3	3	-1	+1
4	4	+1	+1

Table no: 5. Various concentrations of the polymers

Standard	Kollidon(mg)	Polaxamer – 237(mg)
1	20	20
2	40	20
3	20	40
4	20	40

The dependent variable response is as solubility enhancement depends on variable using the fact that the study was designed to be 2² factorial designs, 4 experiments were performed varying the ratio of the independent variables and their effects were observed at three responses (response –cumulative drug release at different intervals.) The results were discussed in the later section.

Formulation and Evaluation Of Dolutegravir Immediate Release Tablets:

Statistically Optimized formula of solid dispersion is used for formulation of tablets

Table No: 6 Composition Of Solid Dispersion Tablets

Sr. No	INGREDIENTS	FORMULA (200 mg)
1	Dolutegravir	20
2.	Polaxamer 237	20
3.	Kollidon	20
4.	MCC	70
5.	Starch	60
6.	Magnesium stearate	5

The tablets were prepared by direct compression method. In this method, tablet ingredients were accurately weighed and formulated in to tablets. Dolutegravir, polaxamer 237, MCC, starch, magnesium stearate and finally talc were added and mix thoroughly and passed through sieve 44 and mixed with lubricant and glidant evenly. The blend was compressed using single punch tablet machine.

Evaluation Of Tablets:

Pre-compression studies:

Angle of Repose, Determination of Bulk Density and Tapped Density, Compressibility Index (Carr’s Index) and Hausner’s Ratio:

Post-compression studies:

Thickness, hardness, Weight variation Friability Test, Drug Content, In -Vitro Drug Release studies.

Stability Studies:

The formulated tablets were stored at room temperature for a period of 3 months. The stability of dosage form was examined at regular intervals and results were discussed in the later section.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Solubility:

Slightly soluble in water and methanol.
0.095mg/ml in water

Table no : 7. Calibration curve of dolutegravir

S.no	Concentration(µgm/ml)	Absorbance(nm)
01	2	0.06±0.004
02	4	0.173±0.003
03	6	0.267±0.005
04	8	0.337±0.006
05	10	0.445±0.005

Fig:1 Calibration curve of Dolutegravir

Phase Solubility:

Table No: 8. Phase solubility of dolutegravir

Sr. NO	COMPONENTS	SOLUBILITY
1	Water	0.095mg/ml in water
2	6.8pH phosphate buffer	0.455 mg/ml

Melting point:190-193°C

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR):
It is a technique used to obtain an infrared

spectrum of absorption or emission of a solid, liquid or gas.

Fig:2 FTIR of dolutegravir pure drug

Fig:3 FTIR of polaxamer – 237

Fig:4 FTIR of Dolutegravir and polaxamer – 237

1. The pure drug dolutegravirexhibited sharp peak at 2234.96 cm⁻¹,1393.32 cm⁻¹, 856.65 cm⁻¹, and 885.53 cm⁻¹ indicating

the presence of C-N stretching, C≡C stretching, C-O-C stretching, C-H bending, and Ar-H bending.(Fig 4.1)

2. For Poloxamer 237 sharp peaks at 2237.60 cm⁻¹, 2165.00 cm⁻¹, and 842.24 cm⁻¹ indicated C-N stretching, C≡C stretching, and C-H bending. (Fig 4.2)
3. For dolutegravir and polaxamer 237 solid dispersion, sharp peaks at 2237.12 cm⁻¹, 2165.40 cm⁻¹, 1391.18 cm⁻¹, and 842.24 cm⁻¹ indicated C-N stretching, C≡C stretching, C-O-C stretching, and Ar-H bending. (Fig 4.3)

Table No: 9. Thin layer chromatography (TLC) studies

Ingredients	Distance travelled (cm)
A. Drug	0.71
B. Drug + excipient	0.74

Note:

The standard Rf value of Dolutegravir is 0.77 cm according to literature. The Rf value of pure drug and drug in combination of excipients is 0.71 and 0.74 cm. Very slight deviation in second decimal was observed. This indicates the compatibility of drug and excipients. This is a qualitative index for drug excipient compatibility studies.

Note:

The studies reported that there is no incompatibility between drug and excipients, so we proceed further to experimental work.

Table No: 10. Cumulative % release of formulations F1 – f18 physical mixture method

S.NO	Formulation	% release
1	F1	19.3±0.002
2	F2	20.8±0.003
3	F3	19.0±0.008
4	F4	19.0±0.004
5	F5	24±0.001
6	F6	24±0.007
7	F7	52.4±0.007
8	F8	48±0.007
9	F9	52±0.007
10	F10	38±0.005
11	F11	42±0.006
12	F12	40±0.009
13	F13	62±0.007
14	F14	65±0.009
15	F15	60±0.006
16	F16	40±0.007
17	F17	42±0.009
18	F18	42±0.005

Among these eighteen formulations F14 is considered as better formulation with 65% release in 2hrs of time and follows First Order respectively.

F14 is considered for further studies.

Table No: 11. Cumulative % release of formulations f19 – f20 (solvent evaporation method and micro oven method)

S.NO	Formulation	% release
1	F19	70.9±0.006
2	F20	58.9±0.003
3	F21	67±0.006
4	F22	53.1±0.006

Among these two formulations F19 is considered as better formulation with 70.9% release rate in 2hrs of time and follows First Order respectively.

Fig:5 Dolutegravir pure drug b) Polaxamer 237 c) Drug:P-237(1:2) x1000

1. SEM images were taken for Dolutegravir (pure drug), polaxamer-237 and a blend of dolutegravir and polaxamer 237.
2. SEM photographs of dolutegravir exhibited high crystallinity with several planes of surfaces.
3. Polaxamer 237 exhibited a spherical shape of granular form of beads.
4. Blend shows that the drug was adsorbed on to the spherical beads and there by enhanced the solubility of dolutegravir and reduces the crystallinity.
5. The size of the particles were found to be 10µ

2²factorial Design:

For interaction effect, KOLLIDON AND POLAXAMER-237 is used

Table No : 12 Dissolution Studies Of Statistically Designed Formulations

File Version	12.0.0.6		
Study Type	Factorial	Subtype	Randomized
Design Type	2 Level Factorial	Runs	7
Design Model	2FI	Blocks	No Blocks
Center Points	3		

Table No: 14 Experimental Design Layout

			Factor 1	Factor 2	Response 1	Response 2	Response 3	Factor 1	Factor 2
Std	Run	Build Type	A:kollidon	B:P-237	1hr	2hr	3hr	Std	Run
			mg	mg	min	min	min		
4	1	NA	40	40	28.4	48.2	68.7	4	1
1	2	NA	20	20	36.5	52.8	80	1	2
7	3	NA	30	30	33.1	50.5	73	7	3
3	4	NA	20	40	32.4	49.5	70.3	3	4
6	5	NA	30	30	33.1	50.5	73	6	5
5	6	NA	30	30	33.1	50.5	73	5	6
2	7	NA	40	20	35.2	51.4	70	2	7

Table No : 15 Final Report Of The 22factorial design

Run Order	Actual Value	Predicted Value	Residual	Leverage	Internally Studentized Residuals	Externally Studentized Residuals	Cook's Distance	Influence on Fitted Value DFFITS	Standard Order
1	68.70	69.02	-0.3214	0.893	-1.732	0.000	6.250 ⁽¹⁾	0.000	4
2	80.00	80.32	-0.3214	0.893	-1.732	0.000	6.250 ⁽¹⁾	0.000	1
3	73.00	72.57	0.4286	0.143	0.816	0.756	0.028	0.309	7
4	70.30	70.62	-0.3214	0.893	-1.732	0.000	6.250 ⁽¹⁾	0.000	3
5	73.00	72.57	0.4286	0.143	0.816	0.756	0.028	0.309	6
6	73.00	72.57	0.4286	0.143	0.816	0.756	0.028	0.309	5
7	70.00	70.32	-0.3214	0.893	-1.732	0.000	6.250 ⁽¹⁾	0.000	2

Table No: 16 ANOVA For Selected Factorial Model Response 3: 3hr

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	81.53	3	27.18	84.55	0.0021	significant
A-kollidon	33.64	1	33.64	104.66	0.0020	
B-P-237	30.25	1	30.25	94.11	0.0023	
AB	17.64	1	17.64	54.88	0.0051	
Curvature	0.0000	0				
Residual	0.9643	3	0.3214			
Lack of Fit	0.9643	1	0.9643			
Pure Error	0.0000	2	0.0000			
Cor Total	82.49	6				

Factor coding is Coded..Sum of squares is Type III – Partial. The Model F-value of 84.55 implies the model is significant. There is only a 0.21% chance that an F-value this large could occur due to noise. P-values less than 0.0500 indicate model terms are significant. In this case A, B, AB are significant

model terms. Values greater than 0.1000 indicate the model terms are not significant. If there are many insignificant model terms (not counting those required to support hierarchy), model reduction may improve your model

Table No: 17 P Values Of Individual Factors And Interaction Between Them

	Intercept	A	B	AB
1hr	33.1143	-1.325	-2.725	-0.675
p-values		< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
2hr	50.4857	-0.675	-1.625	0.025

p-values		< 0.0001	< 0.0001	0.0773
3hr	72.5714	-2.9	-2.75	2.1
p-values		0.0020	0.0023	0.0051

Table No : 18 Solutions Of Optimization

Number	kollidon	P-237	1hr	2hr	3hr	Desirability	
1	20.000	20.000	36.500	52.800	80.000	1.000	Selected
2	20.508	20.000	36.467	52.764	79.746	0.988	
3	20.000	20.464	36.405	52.723	79.775	0.986	
4	20.609	20.000	36.460	52.757	79.695	0.986	
5	20.000	20.657	36.365	52.692	79.681	0.980	
6	21.837	20.000	36.381	52.671	79.082	0.956	

Fig:6 Contour plots of optimized solutions

Fig:7 Responses of the solutions -Prediction vs Desirability

Report of the Optimization:

The Interaction between Kollidone-20mg and Poloxamer- 237 -20 mg would give dissolution of 36.5% at 1hr52.8% in 2 hrs and 80.0% in 3hr The Desirability value (should be close to 1) of 1.00

shows that it is highly likely of the most desirable result to have. Note: The simplest model which we have selected for optimization of various ratios of the polymers was found to be significant statistically.

Pre-Compression Parameters Of Dolutegravir Tablets**Table no: 19 F19 solid dispersion formulation is formulated into tablets by means of direct compression as f23.**

S. No	Formulation	Angle of Repose	Bulk Density (gm/cc)	Tapped Density (gm/cc)	Carr's Index (%)	Hausner's Ratio
1	F23	38°	0.355	0.551	12.32	1.312

Table No: 20- Post Compression Parameters Of Dolutegravir Tablets

S.NO	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Thickness (mm)	% Friability	Assay (%)	Disintegration (min/sec)
1	3.6	2.00	0.344	100	4'21"
2	3.4	2.10	0.160	100	5'20"
3	3.5	2.35	0.079	100	4'45"
4	3.5	2.12	0.184	99	4'24"
5	3.7	2.11	0.160	98	3'27"
6	3.2	2.20	0.129	99	4'35"

Table No: 21 Percent Release Value and R2 Values of Formulated Tablet –F23

S. No	Formulated tablet	% drug release	Zero order	First order
1	F23	81%	0.839	0.971

Table No: 22 Results Of Stability Studies Of F23 Formulation

SNO	TIME (months)	APPEARANCE	HARDNESS (kg/cm ²)	% AMOUNT RELEASE/ 3hr
1	0	White	3-4	81.3
2	1	White	3-4	81.6
3	2	White	3-4	81.8
4	3	White	3-4	81.6

Note: No deviation in the appearance and dissolution parameters of the tablets after storage at room temperature for a period of three months.

CONCLUSION:

The research was focused on polymers to enhance the solubility of Dolutegravir using optimization studies. Out of all polymers, polaxmer -237 was found to be better. Kollidon was found to be next to Polaxmer-237. A factorial 2² design was used for optimization procedure. It was developed to evaluate the interaction and effect of two factors of Polaxamer-237 and Kollidon. FD1 formulation was found to be better with release rate of 80% for a period of 3hr. FD1 mixture (20mg of Polaxmer-237 and 20mg of Kollidon along with drug and other excipients were formulated in to tablets and

evaluated. We observed 81.3% release in 3hr in the case of tablets. Formulated tablets follow first order release kinetics. Remaining precompressional and post compressional parameters are in the limits. We observed the SEM images of the mixture as blend shows that the drug was adsorbed on to the spherical beads of the polymer and there by enhanced the solubility of Dolutegravir and reduces the crystallinity. The size of the particles was found to be 10 μ . The simplest model which we have selected for optimization of various ratios of the polymers was found to be significant statistically. We can implement novel statistical techniques to further optimize the method for better solubility of the drug

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